

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXX. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with Doubly-tridentate Chelating Azo-dye Ligand

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The azodye 1,4-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonic phenylazo)benzene behaves as a doubly-tridentate chelating ligand and forms oxo-bridged tetranuclear complexes with divalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg. The complexes were characterised on the basis of analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, molecular weight, ir, esr and electronic spectral data.

THE azo dyes exhibit both chemotherapeutic and antiseptic properties¹. Some of the azo dyes are used for dyeing food stuffs, for preserving food grains² and as redox-indicator³. Potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates with azo dyes have been reported. Earlier we reported⁴ the preparation and characterisation of polymetallic complexes containing doubly-bidentate azo dyes and Schiff bases. The present work reports the synthesis of a new doubly-tridentate azo dye ligand, 1,4-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonic-phenylazo)benzene (**1**) having $\text{O} \text{---} \text{O} \text{---} \text{N} \text{---} \text{N} \text{---} \text{O} \text{---} \text{O}$ potential donor atoms, and its metal complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of BDH grade. The ligand was prepared by the usual method of preparation of diazonium chloride from *p*-phenylenediamine and reacting it with sulphosalicylic acid in alkaline medium. The resulting azo dye was washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from ethanol (95%) (Found: C, 41.8; H, 2.3; N, 9.1. C₂₀H₁₄O₁₂N₄S₂ required: C, 42.40; H, 2.47; N, 9.39%).

Preparation of the complexes: The metal chlorides in EtOH were separately added to an ethanolic solution of the azo dye ligand in 2 : 1 ratio and the reaction mixture was warmed for ~15 min over a heating mantle. On cooling, concentrated ammonia was added to it dropwise under stirring

and the metal chelates appeared immediately, which were then filtered, washed with EtOH, Et₂O and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal and nitrogen contents in the complexes were determined by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M dimethylformamide. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at room temperature. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10⁻² M DMF) on a Hilger and Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a E-4 spectrometer at room temperature. Molecular weight of the complexes was determined by Rast method using camphor as solvent.

The analytical, physical and spectral data are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : (Found/Calcd.)		Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)
	M	N	
[Co ₄ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈]	15.3 (15.67)	7.2 (7.44)	1 965 (1 513)
[Ni ₄ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈]	15.4 (15.62)	7.3 (7.45)	1 360 (1 512)
[Cu ₄ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₈]	16.4 (16.69)	7.2 (7.35)	1 405 (1 532)
[Zn ₄ L ₂]	18.5 (18.86)	7.8 (8.08)	1 275 (1 395)
[Cd ₄ L ₂]	28.2 (28.57)	7.1 (7.11)	1 425 (1 583)
[Hg ₄ L ₂]	41.2 (41.65)	5.4 (5.81)	1 780 (1 936)

*LH₄ = 1,4-Bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonicphenylazo)benzene.

Results and Discussion

The polymeric complexes have the compositions [M₄L₂(H₂O)₈] and [M'₄L₂], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}; M' = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; LH₄ = 1,4-bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-sulphonicphenylazo)benzene.

The stoichiometrics are further supported by molecular weight data (Table 1).

All the complexes possess high melting points, and are insoluble in common organic solvents but very feebly soluble in DMF. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from the lower conductance values ($5-8 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). All the complexes are quite stable upto 120° indicating the coordinated nature of the water molecules present in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes.

In the ir spectrum of the ligand, the band at 2850 cm^{-1} (OH) is lowered due to $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\cdots\text{O}$ and $\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\cdots\text{N}$ hydrogen bonding. Disappearance of this band in the metal complexes indicates bonding of phenolic OH group to the metal ions. It has been suggested that the positive shift of the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band of the ligand on complexation with metal ion

is indicative of phenolic oxygen bridge $\text{M} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{M}$

in a dinuclear complex⁵. Here in the ligand the sharp band appearing at 1505 cm^{-1} can be assigned to phenolic C-O vibration and in the metal complexes it appears at $\sim 1525 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shows the presence of oxygen-bridged tetrameric species⁶. A new stretching band appearing at $770-80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to phenolic oxygen bridging which occurs more readily via phenolic oxygen atom⁷. Griffith⁸ has observed a similar band at $710-790 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to oxo-bridged skeleton in dimeric complexes. In the present case one sharp peak is observed at $710-750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in support of the polymeric oxo-bridged structure of the complexes. A sharp band appearing at 1580 cm^{-1} ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-$) in the ligand suffers a bathochromic shift of $\sim 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating coordination of one of the azo-nitrogen atoms to the metal ions⁹.

In the ligand, the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ bands appear at 1670 and 1425 cm^{-1} respectively, and in the metal chelates these bands are observed at 1580 and 1385 cm^{-1} with a difference of $\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggestive of the monodentate nature of the carboxylate group. The bands at 3255 (OH), 1130 , 1035 and 650 cm^{-1} in the ligand corresponding to the sulphonic acid group, remain unaffected in the metal complexes indicating the non-coordination of the same group to the metal ions¹⁰. In case of the Co^{II} complex one double hump is observed at $3200-3550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and in case of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes broad bands are observed at $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by the appearance of sharp peaks at ~ 1600 and $\sim 830 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to OH stretching bending and rocking vibrations respectively, and thus indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules in these complexes. The evidence of bonding of the ligand to the metal atoms is obtained tentatively by the appearance bands at 450 (M-O) and 500 cm^{-1} (M-N) in the far-ir spectra of the complexes¹¹.

All the three Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic having lower magnetic moment values. Magnetic moment values of these three complexes

were found to be 2.8, 2.7 and 1.39 respectively. The lower μ_{eff} values are indicative of metal-metal interactions supporting their polynuclear structures¹².

The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex shows ligand field bands at 8820 , 17730 , 21540 and 33200 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and CT transitions respectively. The ligand field parameters Dq (891 cm^{-1}), B (854 cm^{-1}), β_{35} (0.879), Dq/B (1.04), ν_2/ν_1 (2.01) and σ (13.76) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry for the Co^{II} complex. In the electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex, four bands have been observed. The bands at 11500 , 18210 and 27300 cm^{-1} can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively and that at 34320 cm^{-1} is a CT band. The values of spectral parameters Dq (1150 cm^{-1}), B (734 cm^{-1}), β_{35} (0.705), Dq/B (1.56), ν_2/ν_1 (1.58) and σ (41.8) are all in agreement with the octahedral geometry for Ni^{II} complex¹³. The Cu^{II} complex displays a broad asymmetric ligand field band at $13250-14960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (maxima at 14275 cm^{-1}) assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. Both Jahn-Teller and mixed N, O donor atoms contribute to the broadening of this absorption band. Distorted octahedral geometry is suggested for the Cu^{II} complex¹⁴.

The esr spectrum of the complex was recorded at X-band. The g_{av} value (2.06) was evaluated using Kneubuhl's method¹⁵. The esr spectrum is found to be isotropic consisting of a single line characteristic of regular octahedral symmetry. This type of spectrum may result either due to a regular octahedral stereochemistry undergoing a dynamic or pseudo-rotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion or due to grossly misaligned tetragonal axes which may be reducing the symmetry or a chromophore of symmetry lower than octahedral may undergo free rotation¹⁶ or due to the extensive exchange coupling operating between the Cu^{II} ions¹⁷.

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